

METHODOLOGICAL AND THEORETICAL BASES OF ASSESSING FUNCTIONAL LITERACY OF STUDENTS ON CHEMISTRY

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Abstract. *The article provides examples of methodological and theoretical foundations of functional literacy of students in chemistry. The article highlights the educational function of control and evaluation, the diagnostic function of control and evaluation, the preventive function of control and evaluation, the principles of control and evaluation of students' knowledge and skills. The article also contains forms of closed-type test tasks.*

Keywords: *SES, principle, individuality, differentiated approach, integrative testing, adaptive (adapted) testing, criterion-oriented testing.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that the third Renaissance process covers all spheres of public life, one of the important functions of the education system in our country is the creation of new effective methods of upbringing and training the younger generation, meeting the demand for the level of students' knowledge. Achievement is the result of planned learning outcomes. The concept of development of the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 is to create a national system for assessing the level of literacy of students in the public education system from educational modules of the natural direction, applying the principles of individualization into educational process, public education promoted such relevant functions as the development of criteria for assessing the competencies provided for in the standards. Despite the fact that the current bachelor's degree program is built on the competency-based approach of the state educational standard, teaching and assessment methods are mainly aimed at memorizing and explaining educational material and information, developing critical thinking, skills of independent search and analysis of information, and other skills. This requires a deep analysis of targeted methods of control and assessment.

Methods. It is known to everyone that monitoring and assessment of students' knowledge is the most important component of the educational process and requires great skill and creativity from the teacher. The teacher must be able to skillfully determine the time for monitoring and assessing students' knowledge, and, using various methods of monitoring and assessment, he must be able to ensure the effective work of students throughout the lesson. Without monitoring and assessment, pedagogical guidance in the formation of a student's personality, management of students' cognitive activity, their mental and practical work is impossible. The role of monitoring and assessment in achieving the required educational results and improving the educational process is extremely important. Monitoring and assessment allow us to determine the level of students' preparation and fill in the gaps in their knowledge and skills [1].

Monitoring and evaluation is a clearly defined activity, that is, as a pedagogical tool aimed at determining the level of mastering knowledge, skills, competencies determined by the SES, the development of the student as a person associated with knowledge, professional activity; studying the basics of the educational module allows you to increase interest in learning, educate worldview,

thinking, memory and will. Through monitoring and evaluation, you can assess the student's knowledge, as well as the degree of achievement of the educational goal in the educational process, as well as the dynamics of the education quality indicator [2]. A regularly and systematically organized process of monitoring and evaluation teaches the student to work productively, independently assess the level of knowledge he has received, increases his interest in the educational module. Also, monitoring and evaluation of student learning is the basis for assessing the teacher's activities, that is, how clearly the student can explain the educational material and use effective teaching methods, organize an independent learning process for students. Based on the results of monitoring and assessment, the teacher replaces less effective working methods with effective ones, that is, has functional literacy, and also creates broad conditions for acquiring knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies regulated by the SES.

An important function of monitoring and assessing the level of students' proficiency in knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies determined by the SES are knowledge indicators that meet the minimum requirements for the level of professional training of students and must be mastered by the student and consist in assessing their property, their scientific worldview, the formation of environmental and moral education [3-4].

The essence of the educational function of monitoring and assessment is that in the course of completing control and assessment tasks, students systematize, generalize and improve the knowledge they have acquired. Monitoring and assessment, which allow students to acquire and demonstrate new knowledge, applying previously acquired knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies in new and unexpected situations, create the basis not only for the development of attention, thinking, memory of students, but also the expansion of the scope of knowledge.

Figure 1. Components of the management structure

Definitely, the essence of the diagnostic function of monitoring and evaluation is to regularly obtain information about defects, shortcomings, gaps in the knowledge and skills of students, as well as the reasons that cause difficulties in mastering the educational material. Such information allows you to choose effective teaching methods and clearly define the directions for improving these methods and the educational process.

Awareness of the strengths and weaknesses of students' knowledge serves as a guide for the teacher to improve the educational process by having information about his pedagogical skills, working methods and individual characteristics of the student. The results of monitoring and evaluation help the teacher direct students to fill the gaps in their knowledge, help students identify their mistakes and shortcomings and correct them. In addition, based on the results of monitoring and evaluation, the management of the educational institution, parents will have information about the effectiveness of the educational process [7].

Preventive function of monitoring and evaluation. It is known that mastered educational materials leave the memory of students over time. This will be especially noticeable if the student's knowledge and skills do not require application. Regular monitoring and assessment of students' knowledge allows them to acquire new knowledge, as well as consolidate and repeat it, applying previously acquired knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies in new and unexpected situations. Repetition is closely related to monitoring and assessment as a preventive measure that sharpens the student's memory [8].

The following principles of monitoring and assessment of students' knowledge and skills exist:

1. Regularity. Monitoring and assessment as an integral part of the educational process are regularly organized in all forms of training: lectures, laboratory, practical and seminar classes in close connection with the students' educational activities.

2. Impartiality. Monitoring and assessment are correct, transparent, impartial, objective in relation to students' knowledge, deny that the teacher makes incorrect conclusions based on guesses and subjective opinions, without an in-depth study of students, and require assessment based on specific considerations. Monitoring and assessment determine the actual knowledge obtained by students under programs at a certain stage of the educational process [9].

3. Comprehensiveness. Monitoring and assessment cover all sections of the specified program and ensure verification of theoretical knowledge, skills, competence, mental and intellectual potential, and competencies of the student.

4. Individuality. Monitoring and assessment allow observing and studying the level of knowledge of each student, their learning activities, and individual characteristics. Individual independent control and assessment tasks are appropriate for students who are embarrassed to answer in front of the board, cannot give a bold answer, or do not have the courage. In such cases, supporting the student by openly discussing that the student has completed the assigned task well increases his or her self-confidence [10].

5. Stratified approach. In the process of monitoring and assessment, specific characteristics of the module and its sections are taken into account; various monitoring and assessment methods are used based on these characteristics. This eliminates the shortcomings that arise when using a separate monitoring and assessment method.

6. Based on the requirements for the level of preparation for the educational module and the comprehensive study of students, the unity of requirements for the results of monitoring and assessment by those carrying out monitoring and assessment is ensured [11]

7. Monitoring and assessment are organized on the basis of a pre-established classification system at all stages of the educational process, focused on a specific goal.

The effectiveness of teaching in the higher education system depends not only on the variety of methods and forms of monitoring and assessment of students' knowledge and skills, but also on the content of monitoring and assessment.

In the process of monitoring and assessment, the student carries out mental operations, especially analytical and critical activity. Such tasks as classification and definition of professional objects, processes, events, their mutual comparison and obtaining general conclusions require complex mental activity and skills from the student. Monitoring and assessment should have similar tasks. Determining the similarities and differences in the structure and functions of objects and collections depending on the object of study of the educational module, comparing the processes and concepts occurring in the objects and comparing them with each other, such questions and tasks as connecting, drawing conclusions are of great importance in determining the quality of knowledge and the level of students' skills and in improving their professional training [12].

Experiments show that students lack practical skills, abilities and competencies, such as independent work with textbooks, preparing temporary projects, conducting observations in nature, identifying objects, conducting simple experiments. In the process of learning, the teacher helps students develop practical skills: conduct experiments to understand the nature of professional events and processes, conduct observations of objects, observe seasonal changes in nature and processes, work on objects based on these observations. It is necessary to pay attention to such things as determining their adaptation to a new environment, understanding professional diversity. This enhances the content of higher education and teaches the student to understand the features of the object. It is known that the use of visual, natural, verbal demonstration tools and objects in teaching helps students understand the essence of new material. In determining the indicator of the effectiveness and quality of the educational process, monitoring and assessment of the level of students' proficiency in knowledge, skills, qualifications and specific competencies is of great importance. Proper organization of monitoring and assessment requires the teacher to have a clear understanding of the types of monitoring and assessment and their didactic goals. The professor-teacher must use non-standard test tasks in the process of monitoring and assessing the level of students' mastery of knowledge, skills, qualifications, basic and specific competencies related to the educational module. The advantage of test monitoring and assessment over other traditional methods of control and assessment is that this monitoring and assessment allows for the effective use of time allocated for training, covering a large volume of content and quickly determining the results of studying the educational material.

Test control and assessment allow to determine the level of knowledge of all students in a short time, while forming the nature of the students' preparation for each type of activity. In order to increase the students' interest in learning and teach them to think independently and logically, test tasks should be varied in content and form. On the one hand, this does not allow students to get bored with the same thing, and on the other hand, it forms students' creative activity.

A test is a type of standard task used to determine, control and evaluate a person's intellectual development, abilities, willpower, as well as acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications. A test is a type of standardized task of control and assessment that provides a reliable and valid assessment of a conceptually selected variable with the desired statistical properties. In social practice, tests are widely used to determine what profession a person can acquire, whether he is competent or incompetent, talented or mentally retarded, as well as to select individuals for a certain joint activity [13].

At present time tests are divided into the following types (Fig. 2):

Figure 2. Types of test questions in the modern era

Tests are classified according to various characteristics (Fig. 3):

1. By form – open tests, closed tests.
2. By order of creation – standard, non-standard tests.
3. By level of complexity – reproductive, productive, partially research, creative tests.
4. By purpose – informational, diagnostic, educational, motivational, certification.
5. By technology of implementation – printed, programmed tests [14].

Figure 3. Classification of tests by various characteristics

Standard test tasks consist of closed-type tasks with 1 correct answer and 3 alternative answers. Each question is assessed by a certain number of points. The result of a standard test depends on the number of questions answered correctly.

According to the form of the task, tests are divided into two groups:

1) closed tests - in which one correct answer is selected from the given alternative answers, when determining the answer in test tasks based on previously acquired knowledge, the answer is determined by creative thinking, and if it is necessary to determine it (afterwards, the correct answer is determined among the answers) or the task is completed in writing on the answer sheet;

2) open tests - open test tasks require the formation of the correct answer. In this case, you can also mark the answer, or the correct answer will be determined and written down quickly (if the test question contains a clarifying term for the task, the answer will be written down).

Closed-type test tasks have the following form (Fig. 4):

Figure 4. Forms of closed-type test tasks

It is known that different control and assessment tools are used in training to determine the level of knowledge, skills and competencies acquired by students. The use of non-standard test tasks, which are one of such control and assessment tools, in the educational process allows us to determine the level of assimilation of the specified knowledge, skills and qualifications of each student [15].

The use of non-standard test tasks in teaching modules of professional and special training is important for the development of creative and independent thinking in students.

The use of non-standard test tasks in training:

increases the level of professional training of students;

expands scientific horizons;

consolidates the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications of students;

develops students' thinking, independent and creative thinking;

teaches how to solve practical problems;

leads to logical thinking;

creates a basis for the development of students' mental activity.

Non-standard tests differ to a certain extent in content, structure and purposes of use. These test tasks represent not only the knowledge acquired by students, but also their familiarity with the subject and its parts allow for truthful and objective monitoring and assessment of the skills for identifying their unique characteristics.

Non-standard tests are divided into the following types:

1. Integrative tests;

2. Adaptive (adapted) tests;

3. Criterion-oriented tests;

Integrative tests are test tasks that increase in their overall content, form and level of complexity, allowing for a generalized final conclusion about the level of training of an educational institution graduate, representing an integration of disciplines through the concept of several disciplines.

Adaptive tests are automated, allow for an individual approach to students and consist of instructions on the content of the task, the order of execution, the rule, the score that the student can receive as a result of completing this task, and summing up.

The main group of adaptive tests are pyramidal adaptive tests, according to the purpose of use:

average weight, mixed at the student's choice;

will consist of partial research, creative tasks of varying levels of complexity.

Adaptive tests can be successfully used in the modular-credit paradigm of organizing the educational process. To do this, the teacher must be able to create and apply multi-variant test tasks of varying levels of complexity on one topic, chapter, section, course content.

Standard-target testing is carried out in order to determine the general level of students' training, the quality of teaching a given course, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, the effectiveness of the educational process. In this case, the tests consist of tasks of varying levels of complexity: reproductive (easy), productive (moderately difficult), semi-research (difficult), creative, and the criteria for their evaluation are different. Based on the students' assessments in standardized tests, the goal is determined accordingly. To create these test tasks, first of all, the content of the course is analyzed based on the SES, knowledge, skills and competencies are determined, a set of tasks is created to determine them, these tasks are converted into test tasks and tests are conducted, and, finally, students take this course and prepare a conclusion on the level of mastery.

Gaps in students' knowledge are identified and methods for eliminating them are developed using standardized tests. The process of proper use of the above-mentioned non-standard test tasks in the educational process allows for reliable and fair monitoring and assessment of the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications of students.

The problems of using methods for a comprehensive assessment of the quality of students' professional training are as follows:

creation of methodological and software tools for studying the quality of the educational process;

conducting fundamental research in the field of diagnosing the level of acquisition of knowledge, skills, abilities and competencies based on the requirements imposed by the SES on educational modules in educational organizations, through methods of monitoring and assessing students' knowledge;

development and implementation of a program for monitoring the educational process in the higher education system, as well as a comprehensive assessment of the quality of students' professional training;

improvement and implementation of didactic and technological support for a comprehensive assessment of the quality of students' professional training in modules taught in higher education institutions;

the practice of self-monitoring of students in the process of determining the quality of professional training, that is, the creation and implementation of non-standard adaptive test tasks for educational modules using Ispring or My test program [15].

Results. For assessing the acquired functional literacy of students, we will focus on some non-standard test tasks and their preparation. We will also provide brief information on what methods to use when creating these tasks and studying their content. We believe that the study of these prepared tasks will serve as a methodological resource for students and future teachers, as well as professors and teachers of higher education institutions in the formation of functional literacy of students in comprehensive schools where they work.

Surprisingly, while preparing tasks for students on topics related to general and inorganic chemistry, it is possible to form their functional literacy based on Bloom's taxonomy. In Bloom's taxonomy, students acquire competencies of knowledge, understanding, application, analysis and evaluation in the questions given in the tasks. The tasks below are productive test tasks in which students complete tasks based on their previous knowledge.

1. Look at the picture below and identify the correct ideas.

CH ₃ COOH	HCl	H ₂ O	NaCl

- 1) an aqueous solution of acetic and hydrochloric acids dissociates well
- 2) distilled water and crystals of table salt are not electrolytes.
- 3) a solution of table salt is a good electrolyte.

Answer: 1 and 2

2. Look carefully at the picture below and which of the pictures shows non-electrolyte substances.?

Answer: _____

Answer: a and c

3. Explain the process shown in the figure below.

Answer: A) B)

Answer: A) Non-electrolyte solutions B) Electrolyte solutions

Conclusion. By summarising it should be suggested that the use of methods for assessing students' knowledge in the educational process prepares the basis for determining the effectiveness of training and eliminating existing deficiencies. While developing students' functional literacy in chemistry, it is necessary to use types of non-standard test tasks related to the above-mentioned principles of assessment based on information on chemistry, students' creative thinking when preparing tasks.

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